

COVID-19 Era: Students' Role to Look at Problems in Education System during Lockdown Issues in Maharashtra, India

Vikram R. Jadhav¹, Tushar D. Bagul², Sagar R. Aswale³

¹K. K. W Arts, Science and Commerce College Pimpalgaon (Baswant), Tal Niphad (Nashik), MS (India)

^{2,3}K. K. W Arts, Science, Commerce and Computer Science College Chandori, Tal Niphad (Nashik), MS (India)

Corresponding Author: Tushar D. Bagul

ABSTRACT

The coronavirus, which started in Wuhan (China), has spread to developed and underdeveloped countries, with the greatest impact being so far on the developed countries like America, Italy etc. The biggest impact of Lockdown has been on the economy, here we cannot exclude the impact mainly on education, the traditional education that lockdown used to bring to students is now completely shut down somewhere. The impact of lockdown on education has been mentioned in this paper issue, the education issue has become very big and similarly in the future, exams in all schools and colleges in Maharashtra (India) have been cancelled, mainly on traditional education of students and what they think about online education during the lockdown period and its consequences, with the help of a few questions. The information has been collected here this.

Keywords: Covid-19, Lockdown, Online education, WHO

INTRODUCTION

While the corona virus has had a global impact on education and the education-based sector, it is widely agreed that radical changes in the education sector are needed until the corona virus is eradicated. In addition, the WHO states that the corona virus is less likely to be deported and that it is a virus similar to AIDS. The epidemic of corona virus has also changed the way millions of people around the world are educated. The fourth phase of lockdown,

announced or implemented in the country, has had a devastating effect on more than a million students. In addition, 22 other countries have also announced partial "local" closures. With the rapid spread of the corona virus in Asia, Europe, the Middle East, and the United States, these countries have taken swift and decisive action to reduce the development of the disease as a whole. In the last two weeks, there have been several announcements to suspend the attendance of students in schools and universities as well as cancellation of exams. These decisions, aimed at overcoming the crisis, have led to temporary 'home schooling' for millions of students, especially in countries such as China, South Korea, Italy and Iran. Reasons include the most affected countries. These changes have certainly been inconvenient, but they have also given new examples of educational innovation⁴. To help reduce the spread of coronavirus, students from different parts of the world, including India, started reading and learning at home through interactive applications. Most people have access to educational materials through live television broadcasts. As 5G technology becomes more prevalent in countries like China, USA and Japan, learning and teaching anywhere, anytime, teaching and learning is moving towards the adoption of certain types of digital learning concepts, New methods of learning will replace traditional individual classroom learning, from live broadcasts to

“educational influencers” and experiences of virtual reality². Teaching will be a habit that will organize daily life. Educational associations and alliances with various stakeholders, including governments, publishers, education professionals, technology providers, and telecommunications network operators, can take shape that will be combined to use digital platforms as a temporary solution to the crisis. In emerging countries where education is primarily provided by the government, it can become a prevalent and consequential trend for future education. This epidemic is also an opportunity for students to make decisions in this uncertain world, to make informed decisions, to solve problems in a constructive way, and most importantly to adapt to situations where skills need to be learned. To ensure that these skills will be elementary for all students, flexibility must be developed in our educational systems⁶. There is a lot of confusion in the education system of India and students are unable to follow their regular academic routines. Against the backdrop of this emergency and considering the safety of students and their educational issues, most of the institutions have taken initiative to facilitate telecommunication, Skype call, Zoom application and other virtual options to reduce the distance in education. It is training students and teachers to use virtual classrooms and technology to facilitate the exchange of information¹. Undoubtedly, this is a very important time for students. Therefore, the objective of the scheme is to reduce the pressure on the students and help them to use their time in a beneficial way without compromising on quality. Although there are innovative changes in the student body in this Corona era, there are some negative issues, digital issues can create the mental health of the students, these issues the student wanders anywhere⁵.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The research concludes that the coronavirus has an effect on students'

learning, an issue that is mainly surveyed online⁴ and involves total hundred graduate and postgraduate students, and seeks to know what they think about it, and sent students from different areas through social networking and sought their views on the impact of lockdown's periods issues on education, survey issues included a variety of questions, the results of all opinions has mentioned in results and discussion point.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Following the online survey, the results are as follows,

Do you Think Covid-19 Impact on Education?

According to our survey, more than 90 per cent of students think that Lockdown has had a huge impact on education, very few students feel that it has any effect and some students are neutral.

Do you think cancellation of examination is right?

More than 50 per cent of the students feel that the university has made a wrong decision to cancel the exams, an issue that mainly involves smart students, assuming that their past marks have been verified. Only 27.7 percent of students think the university's decision is right and 16.9 percent can't say anything.

How do you see the lockdown period of Covid-19.

More and more students feel that they can't concentrate on their studies, their minds are full of fears about Corona virus, all of this has distracted them, the different daily news is affecting their mental state a lot, so they have to focus on their studies. can't concentrate.

Does this lockdown have a positive impact on students?

Some students feel that there is a positive effect of Lockdown. However, students are learning very different online courses, mainly webinars, Zoom application, Google classroom etc. is using. They are learning a lot from these Lockdown issues.

Which option is good to take examinations in such situation?

Most of the students think that the exam should be done online so that the coronavirus infection is reduced. Some students think that the exam should be taken after the lockdown, but the exam should not be canceled.

which one is effective learning tool in lockdown period?

More than 50% of the students think that it would be more beneficial for the college professors to take hours online because the students have become accustomed to teaching their professors, the students can

absorb it well. There are a lot of teaching mediums available online but students do not feel the effect well.

Students are most affected class during lockdown period.

Greater than Forty-three percent of students feel that lockdown does usually have an effect on their education, more than 41% of students say that a few issues affect lockdown, and 12.3% think they cannot say anything about it.

Does Covid-19 increases expenses on Education?

More than 41% of students think that the expenditure on education will definitely increase during and after Lockdown. 20% of students think that any amount spent on education will be the same as before Lockdown and 18.5% of students think that the cost has not increased and will not increase in any way and the other 20% of students cannot say anything about it.

Do you think Post Covid-19 will create ample opportunities for students in education?

35.4% of students think that Lockdown is an opportunity to change education issues and 35.4% of students don't think this is an opportunity. 18.5% of students are mediators about this and other students can't say anything about it.

CONCLUSION

After taking the opinion of the students, it is understood that Lockdown has a definite effect on education. Due to Lockdown issues, students can't concentrate on their studies and some students say that there is positive impact. Exams should be conducted online only and college professors should take online lectures during the lockdown period. These issues have increased the cost of education to some extent and these issues have not only affected the education sector but also all sectors. Some students also think that it is an opportunity to innovate on lockdown issues.

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